

ALISHER NAVOIY AND THE UZBEK GHAZAL TRADITION OF THE 20TH CENTURY

Haydarova Gulhayo Ahmadaliyevna

PhD in Philological Sciences

Kokand State University

Email: h.gulhayoxon90@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15580913>

Abstract: This article explores the influence of the ghazal tradition of Alisher Navoi on the works of 20th-century Uzbek ghazal poets such as Asqarali Hamroali og'li Charxiy, Sobir Abdulla, and Habibiy. It analyzes the continuity of classical poetic traditions in the ghazals of these poets, as well as the unique stylistic features characteristic of each individual writer. The study also provides an overview of the principles of divan (collected poetry) compilation in classical literature and the specific approaches to divan creation in the 20th century.

Keywords: ghazal tradition, literary heritage, creative individuality, master-apprentice, radif (refrain), literary influence, imagery, poetic device, personification.

In classical literature, Alisher Navoi outlined the principles for compiling a divan based on his observations of previously created divans in the preface to his *G'aroyib us-sig'ar* collection. According to him, a divan should begin with a preface, include hamd (praise of God) and na't (praise of the Prophet), start with ghazals, conclude with 32 letters instead of 28, and initially feature ghazals on themes of hamd or na't. Furthermore, it should contain couplets related to enlightenment and moral advice, and the idea presented in the opening couplet (matla) should be developed until the concluding couplet (maqta').

In analyzing the ghazals of Sobir Abdulla, Charxiy, and Habibiy through the lens of traditionalism, it is important to note certain unique aspects of 20th-century Uzbek ghazal poetry. These distinctive features are especially evident in the divans compiled by the poets themselves during their lifetimes.

Firstly, each divan begins with a preface. In this regard, it is notable that Habibiy's divan opens with a prose preface, while Sobir Abdulla's divan includes a 31-line poetic preface primarily focused on praising the era and explaining the reasons behind compiling the divan. In Charxiy's divan, a 42-line preface states that the poet compiled his divan at the age of seventy and mentions the names of Furqat and Muqimiy. Interestingly, none of the three poets' divans include traditional hamd or na't ghazals.

Secondly, while in the divans compiled prior to the 20th century the ghazals were arranged according to the order of letters in the Arabic alphabet, the

Devon collections by Sobir Abdulla (1965) and Charxiy (1972) were published based on the sequence of letters in the Cyrillic alphabet (a, b, v, g, etc.). However, unlike his contemporaries, Habibiy's Devon, compiled in 1960 and reprinted three times (in 1960, 1975, and 1980), retained the classical tradition and arranged its poems according to the order of letters in the Arabic script.

Thirdly, by the 20th century, the practice of assigning titles to ghazals had emerged. It is true that in Alisher Navoi's divans we find general section titles such as "The beginning of the afflictions of the letter Alif from the G'aroyib" or "The manifestation of beauties of the letter Jim from the Navodir," yet these are not individual titles for each ghazal. Rather, they serve to distinguish a group of approximately 115 to 130 ghazals associated with a particular letter. Each of Navoi's ghazals is instead identified by a number.

In contrast, the ghazals of Habibiy, Sobir Abdulla, and Charxiy were given specific titles based on the following approaches:

- according to the radif (refrain) of the ghazal;
- derived from the content or theme of the ghazal itself;
- assigned during the editorial and publishing process by editors.

These titles were typically formulated using a word, phrase, or compound expression. For example, the titles of Charxiy's ghazals include such phrases as "Qo'qon loyi," "Yodlar zamon, Muqimiy," "Vafo sevarim," and others, often drawn from the opening elements of the rhyme or radif. A similar pattern can be seen in Habibiy's ghazals, where titles such as "Sharob," "Suhbat," "O't," and "Bahs" reflect the radif, while others like "San'ating," "Ozod," and "Keldi yor" are taken from the rhyming scheme.

Sobir Abdulla adopted a distinctive approach to titling ghazals. He selected entirely new couplets or lines—often his own aphorisms—that matched the theme or essence of the poem to serve as its title. This practice is unique, not seen in either 15th-century or 20th-century ghazal traditions. These titles were typed according to the order of Cyrillic alphabet letters in use at the time and reflected the sequence of ghazals in the divan.

Some of the poet's titles also provide information about the historical context in which the ghazal was written.

From the title of this ghazal, it becomes evident that it was written during the poet's youth while he was in the Osh region. In our opinion, all the titles in the divan appear to have been assigned later, during the process of organizing the collection. This is suggested by the fact that the divan was published in 1965, yet in the title, the poet acknowledges that he composed the ghazal during his

youth. The ghazal was written in 1940, corresponding to the poet's most productive period, at the age of 35.

Some of the titles in Sobir Abdulla's divan also serve the function of clarifying certain ambiguities within the ghazals. For instance, in a ghazal beginning with the matla mentioning a playful river in a specific region, the name of the district (rayon) remains undisclosed until the end of the poem. To resolve this uncertainty for readers and clarify the setting, a separate couplet indicating the name "Kosonsoy" is used as the title.

It would not be an exaggeration to state that Asqarali Hamroali og'li Charxiy dedicated his entire creative effort to promoting the classical aruz meter, which was struggling to survive under the literary constraints of his time. In the preface to his *Devon*, he explicitly states: "I feel a stronger inclination towards classical literature... especially satire." Although the poet himself acknowledges his affinity for satire, the majority of his ghazals are not satirical in nature.

In Habibi's ghazals titled "O'qing" (Read), "Mo'tabar" (Respectable), and "Bilim" (Knowledge), which range from 7 to 11 couplets each, the poet aims to awaken ignorant individuals from their slumber and calls upon them to pursue education and value time. He emphasizes the power of science, its ability to conquer the world, even to subjugate the universe, and warns against wasting life. Although these three ghazals were written in different years — 1935, 1942, and 1967 respectively — they all share the central message that acquiring knowledge is a timeless and urgent duty. For example, in the ghazal "Bilim", the lyrical speaker asserts that the world is entering an era of renewal and that the most advanced countries are experiencing transformation, innovation, and progress. Hence, the poet compares knowledge to "a great treasure," "a mighty river in motion," "an arrow and bow," and "the sun of the world." He laments those who reject knowledge, portraying them as devoid of joy and desire for learning, describing their perception of knowledge as akin to the mythical bird Anqā (the unattainable).

The poet's struggle against ignorance is reflected in several other poems as well. In the ghazal titled "Xilma-xil odam" (Various People), he evaluates humanity — the descendants of Adam — not by their physical attributes, but by their intellectual and cognitive abilities. He categorizes people based on their levels of thought and insight, stating that some claim to know while in fact knowing nothing. In the final lines of the ghazal, the poet emphasizes that an ignorant person, despite appearing human, cannot be considered truly human. He laments that the world is full of such individuals. In the closing couplet

(maqta'), the poet turns to himself, saying: "Open your eyes, O Habibi! If you remain ignorant, your condition will be dire. Do not be indifferent or neglectful of the events occurring around you."

In conclusion, it may be said that the 20th-century Uzbek ghazal poets such as Habibi, Charxiy, and Sobir Abdulla, while depicting contemporary realities, remained committed to the continuation of classical literary traditions. Influenced by the ideological context of their time, they engaged with contemporary themes, yet managed to maintain a high level of intellectual discourse that continues to resonate with today's readers. Trusting that future readers would grasp the deeper meanings within their ghazals, these poets skillfully embedded their protests, conclusions, and creative responses to contemporary events within the lines of verse. Moreover, all three poets, drawing inspiration from Alisher Navoi's mastery of poetic imagery, succeeded in continuing the literary tradition while reflecting contemporary reality in a distinctive and original manner.

References:

1. Komilova, M. (2024). LANGUAGE AND SOCIAL INEQUALITY: A PRAGMATIC PERSPECTIVE. University Research Base, 809–813. Retrieved from <https://scholar.kokanduni.uz/index.php/rb/article/view/732>
2. Komilova, M. (2024). THE POWER OF CONCEPTS: EXPLORING THEMES AND THEIR MANIFESTATIONS IN LITERARY TEXTS. University Research Base, 814-817.
3. NO, P. (2025). The role of cognitive linguistics in language evolution.
4. NO, P. The role of cognitive linguistics in language evolution.
5. RAJAPOVA, M. ALLEGORIK VOSITALARNING LINGVOKOGNITIV VA LINGVOPRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Я ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ, 197.
6. Sobirova, N., & Rajapova, M. (2024). EASY TEACHING AND LEARNING STRATEGIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL. Models and methods in modern science, 3(4), 122-124.
7. Rajapova, M., & Mamajonov, A. (2023). Linguistic and cultural characteristics of allegorical devices used in a literary text. Society and innovations, (4), 2181-1415.
8. Rajapova, M. (2021). Lingvoculturology and its peculiarities as new branches of contemporary linguistics. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
9. Rajapova, M. (2022). Allegorical means specific to oral speech. Scienceweb academic papers collection.
10. Haydarova, G. (2024). ALISHER NAVOIY AN'ANALARI VA XX ASR
11. O 'ZBEK G 'AZALIYOTI. Alisher Navo'i and 21 st century, 1(1).

12. NAVOI, A., & BABUR, Z. M. (2022). RESEARCH AND EDUCATION.
13. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳ. Г. (2021). НАВОИЙ ВА СОБИР АБДУЛЛА. ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI, 1(2).
14. Ahmadaliyevna, H. G. (2021). Talmeh or alluziya. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(9), 772-779.
15. Ahmadaliyevna, H. G. (2022). Interpretation of the Image of the Heart in the Poems of Habibi, Charkhi and Sabir Abdullah. European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science, 6, 621-626.
16. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳ. Г. (2022). Собир Абдулла, Чархий Ва Ҳабибий Ғазалиётининг Вазн Хусусиятларига Доир.

